

PREVALENCE AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF ANEMIA AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN: A HOSPITAL-BASED STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Gestational anemia remains a major public health concern, particularly in developing countries. This hospital based prospective observational study evaluated the prevalence, severity, and associated risk factors of anemia among pregnant women attending a tertiary care hospital in Tamilnadu. Out of 215 antenatal women screened, 83 (38.6%) were found to be anemic. Most cases were identified in the second and third trimesters, with mild and moderate anemia being predominant. Rural residence, multiparity, and dietary inadequacies were significant associated factors. The study highlights the importance of early screening, nutritional counselling, and adherence to iron and folic acid supplementation to reduce maternal and neonatal complication.

KEYWORDS: Gestational anemia, pregnancy, Iron deficiency, Maternal health.

INTRODUCTION

Gestational Anemia is a common complication of pregnancy and a serious global public health problem.^[1] The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that 40% of pregnant women worldwide are anemic, with this condition being particularly prevalent developing countries.^[2] This condition is particularly prevalent in low- and middle-income countries, where nutritional deficiencies, infectious diseases, and inadequate healthcare systems contribute to its high burden. In India, the risk of anemia is higher due to wide range of factors such as insufficient knowledge, low income, and illegal abortion. It is the second leading cause of maternal deaths in India.^[3,4]

According to WHO, during pregnancy, anemia is identified by hemoglobin levels less than 11.0g/dl and may be divided into three levels of severity mild anemia (Hb levels 9 to 10.9g/dl), moderate anemia (Hb levels 7 to 8.9g/dl), and severe anemia (Hb levels less than 7g/dl).^[5,6]

Data from the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) 4 show that anemia is 50.3% more common in India than in Karnataka. Nearly 50% of the population is anemic, with rural areas generally bearing a heavier burden than urban ones.^[7]

Anemia in pregnant women has been regarded as detrimental to the fetal growth and pregnancy outcome.^[8] In the mother, Anemia is associated with reduced physical performance, increased fatigue level, reduced cognitive performance, increased risk of infection and hospitalization, and inhibited lactation.^[9,10] Also, pregnant women with anemia are at a greater risk of perinatal mortality and morbidity. Adverse consequences the fetus include spontaneous abortion, premature delivery, intrauterine fetal death, low birth weight, small for gestational-age babies, hypertension, neurologic impairment, etc.^[11,12]

The main reason is that Gestational Anemia is primarily caused by Iron-deficiency which results in reduced Hb levels and decreased oxygen carrying capacity, it occurs due to the increased Iron requirements associated with fetal growth and the expansion of maternal blood volume. In India, anemia due to iron deficiency affects 80% of pregnant women. In the majority of the world, anemia is one of the leading causes of disease and mortality. Anemia during pregnancy has a negative impact on both the mother and the unborn child's health.^[13,14]

Folate and vitamin B12 deficiencies are particularly concerning as they are vital for proper fetal development and placental function.^[15] Folate is crucial for DNA synthesis and cellular division, while vitamin B12 is essential for the maturation of red blood cells.^[14]

- ❖ Mild anemia: Hb 10.0 mg/dl – 10.9 mg/dl,
- ❖ Moderate anemia: Hb 7.0 mg/dl – 10.0 mg/dl,
- ❖ Severe anemia: Hb less than 7.0 mg/dl.

The levels of hemoglobin used for the classification of anemia in pregnant women as mild, moderate, severe anemia were those recommended by the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), which is defined as follows:

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A descriptive prospective study was conducted over a period of 1 month from November 20, 2025 to December 20, 2025 from the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Medical College and Hospital (DSMCH), Siruvachur, Perambalur district. A total 215 pregnant women coming to the antenatal OPD were screened for anemia using laboratory tests and 132 women who were not anemic were excluded. A total 83 patients were enrolled in the study.

Inclusion criteria

- Pregnant women \geq 18 years attending the antenatal clinic of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Medical College and Hospital, Siruvachur.
- Any gestational age – First, Second, Third Trimester.
- Hb% less than 11gm%.

Exclusion criteria

- Non pregnant women
- Hematologic disorder – Thalassemia, Sickle cell disease
- Blood transfusion within the past 4weeks.
- Severe chronic illness.

A total sample comprised of 215 pregnant women who were interviewed by using self-structured questionnaire for data collection, and classification of anemia was performed according to Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR); among them, 83 pregnant women were suffering from mild, moderate, and severe anemia.

Self-structured tool pertaining to various independent variable in sociodemographic profile such as age, education, family history, residence, blood group, intervals of pregnancy, and level of Hb. It also encompasses of contributing factors including H/O abortion, consumption of iron, and folic acid tablets and Dietary habits during present pregnancy. Determining the outcome variable level of hemoglobin was considered through laboratory report. Pregnant mother with Hb level less than 11 gm/dl was considered as anemic further classification of mild, moderate, and severe anemia were those recommended by the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), which is defined as follows:

- Mild anemia: Hb 10.0 mg/dl- 10.9 mg/dl.

- Moderate anemia: Hb 7.0 mg/dl- 10.0 mg/dl.
- Severe anemia: Hb less than 7 mg/dl.

Approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee prior to the commencement of the study. Each participant was explained in detail about the study and written informed consent was obtained prior to the data collection. The study sample was explained the purpose of the study and informed regarding potential benefit in health, which eventually helped them in making decisions regarding participation in the study.

RESULTS

A total 215 pregnant women coming to the antenatal OPD during this study study period (November 10,2025 to December 9,2025) out of which 132 women had Hb% above 11Gm/dl they are excluded. A total 83 patients were enrolled in the study. The incidence of anemia rates in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan medical hospital was 38 (45%) were mild, 37 (44%) were moderate, and 8(9%) were severe during the present study period.

The 83 anemic women were include in this study. Mean age of the participant was 38.6%. Maximum number of anemic women were in the age group of 25-30 years (39.76%) followed by (36.76%) in 20-24 years and (13.26%) in more than 30 years. The least anemia was seen in the age group less than 20 years (10.84%) [table 1]. Of which antenatal women 9.64% were primary educated, 38.56% are secondary educated and 51.80% are graduated respectively. Anemia is seen more in the graduated women (51.80%) followed by secondary educated women (38.56%) and least percentage of anemia were seen in the primary educated women (9.64%) [table 2]

Table 1: Age Distribution.

AGE	Mild anemia	Moderate anemia	Severe anemia	Total
<20	3	4	2	9 (10.84%)
20 - 24	15	12	3	30(36.14)
25 - 30	16	15	2	33(39.76%)
>30	4	6	1	11(13.26%)

Table 2: Educational Status.

Educational qualification	Mild anemia	Moderate anemia	Severe anemia	Total
Primary	4	2	2	8(9.64%)
Secondary	12	17	3	32(38.56%)
Graduated	22	18	3	43(51.80%)

Based upon their Residing Area a greater number of anemias are seen in the rural area (65%) and less numbers are seen in the urban area (35%) [table 3]. By Analysing their dietary habits maximum number of anemias were seen in non-vegetarian women (84%) and less number were in the vegetarian women (16%) [table 4]. Prevalence of anemia occurs in primigravida (49%) and multigravida (51%) were almost equal but 80% of severely anemic patient were multigravida [table 5]. Based on their trimester maximum number of anemias are seen in the 3rd trimester (44.58%) followed by 2nd trimester (39.76%) and minimum percentage were seen in the 1st trimester (15.66%) [table 6]. By comparing their blood groups A+ has (20.48%), A-ve has (1.20%), B+ has (43.38%), B-ve has (4.82%), AB+ has (4.82%), AB-ve has (1.20%), O+ve has (19.28%), O-ve has (4.82%). Anemia are more seen in the B+ve women (43.38%), followed by O+ve women (19.28%). least numbers are seen in the A-ve and AB-ve women (1.20%) respectively.

Table 3: Area of Residency.

RESIDENCE	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
RURAL	54	65%
URBAN	46	35%

Table 4: Dietary Habits.

DIETARY HABITS	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
VEGETARIAN	13	16%
NON-VEGETARIAN	70	84%

Table 5: Number of pregnancies.

GRAVIDA	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
PRMI	41	49 %
MULTI	42	51 %

Table 6: based on their Trimester.

TRIMESTER	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
1 st TRIMESTER	13	15.66 %
2 nd TRIMESTER	33	39.76 %
3 rd TRIMESTER	37	44.58 %

Table 7: Based on Their Blood Group.

BLOOD GROUP	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
A +ve	17	20.48 %
A-ve	1	1.20 %
B+ve	36	43.38 %
B-ve	4	4.82 %
AB+ve	4	4.82 %

AB-ve	1	1.20 %
O+ve	16	19.28 %
O-ve	4	4.82 %

DISCUSSION

In this present study the percentage and severity of anemia in pregnant women was analysed. The prevalence of anemia in pregnancy in our study was 38.66%. The severity of anemia was graded as per WHO classification of anemia. 45.79% of the women were mild anemic, 44.58% were moderately anemic and 9.63% were severely anemic. As per our study anemia was most prevalent in the age 25-30 years old women (39.76%), indicating that the anemia predominantly affects women in their peak reproductive years. Regarding the education qualification the anemia are more prevalent in graduated women (51.80%). In our study of dietary habits, the anemia was more common in non- vegetarian women (84%). Comparing the primigravida with multigravida women the anemia causing is slightly higher in multigravida. By analysing their blood group, the anemia was more common in B+ve women (43.38%). In studies by bison et al and Sowmya et al they have also reported the same distribution (50%).

CONCLUSION

Anemia is more prevalent in rural pregnant women. Demographic factors play a significant role. Education level has no much significant impact as per the present study. Treating anemia in pregnant women will go a long way in improving maternal and fetal outcome. To overcome this Iron tablet can be distributed at school to young girls to prevent anemia in future women. Educating young girls regarding hygiene, nutrition diet, iron supplement even in pre pregnancy stage will prevent anemia to a great extent during pregnancy. Hence a future healthy younger generation can be produced.

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